

Influence of Obesity on Brain 5-HT₆ Receptor Expression: an *In-Vivo* Study with the PET Radiotracer [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P

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Keywords

5-HT₆ receptor, [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P, obesity, diet-induced obesity, specific PET radiotracer

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Abstract

In 2016, more than 1.9 billion adults were overweight. Estimations based on current trends suggest that approximately 25 % of the population will be obese in 2025. Better understanding of obesity pathophysiology will help to develop future therapeutics. Using antagonists, agonists or knock-out animals, serotonin subtype 6 receptor (5-HT₆), have shown to be critically involved in appetite reduction and weight loss. However, it is not known if the pathological cascade triggered by obesity modifies 5-HT₆ receptor density in the brain. In this study, we aim to explore the influence of a diet-induced obesity (DIO) rat model on the 5-HT₆ receptor expression using the PET radiotracer [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P. The primary goal is to detect *in-vivo* changes in the cerebral uptake of the 5-HT₆ radiotracer changes before and after a 10-week DIO, while measuring whole-body fat accumulation with MRI. Using control animals under normal diet, and a genetic obesity model (Zucker rats), the secondary goal is to compare final 5-HT₆ receptor levels between the three groups (DIO, genetic obesity and control diet). In this stage 1 registered report, we provide preliminary results showing the feasibility of our study: i) DIO model was tested and led to 25.5 % increase in fat measured on MRI, ii) regional 5-HT₆ receptor densities were reliably quantified in PET test-retests following tariquidar pre-injection to increase blood-brain barrier passage of the radiotracer [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P. This multimodal imaging study is expected to yield original results for the understanding of the physiopathology of obesity and the implication of 5-HT₆ receptors in this disease.

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), worldwide obesity has almost tripled since 1975. WHO estimates that in 2016 over 650 million adults were obese representing 13 % of the adult population. Children are also suffering from obesity which prevalence has risen from 4 % in 1975 to 18 % in 2016 (1). Obesity, defined by a body mass index (BMI) greater or equal to 30, is considered as a high-risk factor in many chronic diseases. In a large prospective of more than one million adults, men and women with high BMI have relative risk of death of 2.58 and 2.00 respectively compared to people with BMI from 23.5 to 24.9 (2). Obesity has been demonstrated to be associated with a higher risk of developing cardiovascular disease (2), diabetic renal or hepatic disorders (3), cancers (4) or mental disorders (5), leading to a higher risk of overall mortality (3). European guidelines suggest reducing weight (and BMI) and waist circumferences using three ways: lifestyle modification, pharmacotherapy and bariatric surgery (6). Pharmacological treatment helps compliance, prevents comorbidities and improves quality of life. Currently, orlistat, a fatty acid synthase inhibitor, is authorized by several international medical agencies for the treatment of obesity (7). Orlistat has been shown to reduce weight and waist circumferences in two randomized clinical trials (8,9). Other drugs have been developed such as lorcaserin or the association phentermine/topiramate but received mixed reviews by agencies, being whether authorized, withdrawn from market (10) or unauthorized (11). Thus, new therapeutics pathways need to be explored.

Serotonin subtype 6 receptors (5-HT₆) were discovered in the 90s, and are almost exclusively distributed in the central nervous system, mainly in striatum, pre-frontal cortex and hippocampus (12). 5-HT₆ receptors were first targeted for the treatment of cognitive disorders such as Alzheimer's disease, but the results of clinical studies using antagonists have been disappointing so far (13). However, these receptors were also shown to be implicated in appetite regulation and weight variations and have been considered as potential targets for anti-obesity drugs (14). First, preclinical studies using 5-HT₆ receptor-directed antisense oligodeoxynucleotides reported a decrease in food consumption leading to a lower body weight (15). Second, treatment with 5-HT₆ receptor antagonists resulted in similar effects (16–19). Paradoxically, chronic treatment with a 5-HT₆ partial agonist induced sustained weight loss and decrease food intake after diet-induced obesity (DIO) (20). These mixed results showed the complexity of the 5-HT₆ receptor mechanism in food consumption. Thus, additional studies are required to better understand 5-HT₆ receptor physiology. Finally, a mouse model expressing a non-functional mutant of 5-HT₆ receptor (C57BL/6) appeared to be resistant to DIO (21), and this finding was also observed in knock-out 5-HT₆ receptor mice (22). Thus, a vast amount of scientific literature points to a major involvement of 5-HT₆ receptors in the regulation of food consumption and the development of obesity. However, potential changes of the receptor expression

and density in the brain remain unexplored so far. Such chronic changes would critically improve the knowledge of pathophysiological mechanisms and impact treatment strategies in obesity.

In this context, we aim to explore the influence of a DIO model and genetic obesity on the 5-HT₆ receptor density using [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P a novel PET radiotracer of 5-HT₆ receptors, previously developed and validated in our laboratory (23). [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P is the first fluorinated radiotracer with high affinity and selectivity for 5-HT₆ receptors (24), hence allowing cerebral 5-HT₆ receptor changes to be tracked *in-vivo* through the quantification of radiotracer uptake in the brain. Based on the literature cited above we hypothesized that: (1) DIO will modify [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P uptake compared to the basal density; (2) [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P uptake will be similarly modified in DIO animals or in genetically-proned animals, compared to control animals (3) significant correlation will be observed between obesity development and [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P uptake. [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P radiotracer uptake surrogates 5-HT₆ receptors density.

Methods

Study design

The study is designed to detect a 20 % difference in [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P cerebral uptake after a 10-week high-fat diet in male Wistar rats. Diet composition and duration were chosen according to literature (25). Rat strain was selected after a pilot experiment (see Preliminary results section). Day one of study protocol will be defined by the day of starting diet. During this period, animal weight and food consumption will be recorded twice a week. MRI at 7T will be used to monitor whole-body fat increase (by imaging and spectroscopy) and will be performed at baseline and repeated when animals reach a maximal weight of 500-600 g (after 5 weeks of diet – technically impossible with bigger animals). PET will be performed at baseline (before diet initiation) and after 10 weeks. PET acquisition protocol and [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P quantification have been tested and optimized in test-retest experiments (premedication with a P-gp inhibitor, static acquisition 40 minutes after radiotracer injection, atlas-based quantification with SUVr: see Preliminary results section). Animals will be sacrificed after final PET and brains will be collected. A permeability test with Evans blue dye in three rats for DIO and control group respectively will be performed to assess blood-brain barrier (BBB) integrity (26). Results will be provided as supplemental data.

Additional, exploratory analysis will be performed to compare [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P uptake changes in control animals (Wistar rats under a 10-week control diet) and in a genetic model of obesity (Zucker rats under a 10-week control diet). The number of animals in each group (main group of DIO Wistar rats: n = 18; additional groups of control-diet Wistar rats and Zucker rats: n = 6 each) is justified in the Statistical analysis section.

All experiments are carried out under a protocol approved by the local ethical review board (“Comité d’éthique pour l’Expérimentation Animale Neurosciences Lyon”, registration code: C2EA – 42), authorized by the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research (n°25505-2020052514313066V4), and are in accordance with European directives on the protection and use of laboratory animals (Council Directive 2010/63/UE, French decree 2013-118).

Animals and diet

Male rats Wistar (Charles River Laboratories®; 5-6 weeks old, 175-200 g) and Zucker rats obese prone (CrI:ZUC(Orl)-*Lep^{fa}*, Charles River Laboratories®, 5-6 weeks old, 175-200 g) will be given a minimum of seven days to acclimate to the conventional housing facility, under temperature-controlled (range 20-24°C) conditions, and a 12:12h light-dark cycle, with lights on at 07:00 and off at 19:00. Animals will be divided in three different groups. First, Wistar rats will be randomized to “DIO group” (n = 18), fed with high-fat high-sucrose nutrition (pellets SAFE® U8955, 246HF, composition in energy content: proteins 15.9 %, lipids 45.5 % and nitrogen-free extract 38.6 %), and “control group” (n = 6), fed with standard chow (pellets of wheat and corn, Teklad Global 18 % Protein Rodent Diet, ENVIGO). The third “Zucker group” (n = 6) will spontaneously develop obesity when fed with standard chow. All animals will be given access to tap water ad libidum. Exclusion criteria is the occurrence of a serious adverse event in rat (suffering, intolerance to diet, death...)

Radiosynthesis of the 5-HT₆ receptor radiopharmaceutical and quality controls

The chemical nitro-precursor of our 5-HT₆ PET radiotracer, [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P, is synthesized as described previously (23). Radiolabeling with ¹⁸F is performed extemporaneously, on the days of the in-vitro experiments, according to our published protocol (24). Briefly, radiosynthesis use an automated Neptis fluorination module (OOC, Belgium). [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P quality control determine radiochemical purity and molar activity on analytical HPLC assay at the end of each production run, guaranteeing the radiopharmaceutical quality of the radiotracer used for the following in-vitro experiments: i.e., molar activity > 340 GBq/μmol and radiochemical purity > 98 %.

Imaging protocol

All imaging sessions are performed under isoflurane anesthesia delivered in air by approved systems (TEM Segla). Rectal temperature is continuously measured and maintained at 37 ± 1°C.

PET

Hydration with 2 mL of physiologic serum i.p. will be performed after the start of anesthesia. Tariquidar (8 mg/kg) will be administered in the caudal vein to enhance BBB cross. Thirty minutes later, [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P (37 kBq/g), radiolabeled according to a previously described protocol (23), will be administered in the caudal vein. Static brain PET acquisition will then be performed 40 minutes after radiotracer injection and during 20 minutes on a PET/CT Inveon (Siemens) with animals on prone position, head centered in the field of view, and monitoring of respiratory rate. CT scanning will be performed to correct attenuation and scatter. Images will be reconstructed with attenuation and scatter correction by 3D ordinary Poisson ordered subsets expectation-maximization (OP-OSEM3D) with 4 iterations and a zoom factor of 2. The reconstructed volume is constituted of 159 slices of 128 × 128 voxels, in a bounding box of 49.7 × 49.7 × 126 mm³ and with voxel size 0.388 × 0.388 × 0.796 mm³. Images will be analyzed with the INVEON Research Workplace (IRW, Siemens).

A limited number of regions of interest (ROIs) involved in food intake for which we have an a priori hypothesis, will be used for analysis, so as to performed multiple exploratory comparisons: striatum, hypothalamus, hippocampus, amygdala and frontal cortex. For Wistar rats, these anatomical ROIs will be automatically derived from the recently described SIGMA atlas, which provides with a full brain coverage of Wistar rat strain (27), after manual positioning of the PET images on the corresponding MRI template. In case of a notable increase of brain size after 10 weeks, MRI templates (average images from 3 to 5 animals) will be built at week 1 and 10 and spherical ROIs will be manually drawn in the above-cited anatomical regions for Wistar groups. For Zucker rats, spherical ROIs will be drawn manually in the above-cited anatomical regions because no brain atlas is available for this specific strain. Uptake will be expressed in Bq/cm³ normalized for the injected dose corrected and weight to obtain standardized uptake values (SUV). Each region SUV will be normalized to white matter cerebellum SUV considered as a reference region to obtain a SUV ratio (SUVr). This region has the lowest uptake of [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P and is known not to express 5-HT₆ receptor.

Parametric images of SUVr will be calculated for DIO rats at week 1 and 10 after manual drawing of the normalization ROI in the cerebellum. Individual PET images will be realigned and spatially normalized on a custom PET template which will be registered onto the imported MRI template (with a voxel size of 0.1 x 0.1 x 0.2 mm). The quality of the registration will be visually checked between all images to verify that they fit well together and match the MRI template in terms of cortical boundaries. Each PET volume will be smoothed using an isotropic Gaussian filter (1.0 × 1.0 × 1.0 mm).

MRI

The MR imaging experiments will be conducted on a 7T small animal Bruker system (Bruker, Ettlingen, Germany) equipped with a 12-cm actively shielded bore and 440 mT/m gradient set. The animals will be placed on prone position in a dedicated plastic bed (Bruker Biospec Animal Handling Systems,

Germany), adapted with a stereotactic system allowing the animal immobilization. A respiratory sensor will be placed on the animal's abdomen in order to constantly monitor the respiration rate.

The MR acquisitions will be performed using a whole-body emission-reception body coil (72 mm). First, a reference scan (3 directions) will be acquired to adjust shim and frequency parameters over the entire body and to position the coronal stack for whole body fat analysis (subcutaneous and visceral fat, respectively). For the water image, a 2D T1-weighted respiratory gated spin echo sequence (MSME) with fat suppression will be acquired with the following parameters: TR/TE = 6164/8.1 msec, a matrix size of 256 × 128 for a voxel size of 586 × 625 × 1000 μm³. Fat images will be acquired using the cloned MSME sequence of the water image with a B1 shift frequency of 1050 Hz corresponding to the water-fat frequency gap at 7T (300 MHz). A whole-body spectrum (SinglePulse, with the following parameters TR = 1000 ms, NA 240, TA 4 min) will be then acquired to determine fat / water ratio. The spectrum analysis will be performed within the TopSpin (Bruker ParaVision 5.1) post-processing tool. After phase and baseline correction, the areas under the curve (AUC) of the water and fat peaks will be quantified and expressed as a % of sum of peak integrals. The total fat volume (intra-abdominal and subcutaneous) measurement will be performed under the ImageJ software by binarizing the fat images, and then extracted using a dedicated volume quantification plugin and expressed in cm³.

Statistical analyses

Statistical analyses will be performed as follows to respond to the different hypotheses.

Two approaches will be tested to assess hypothesis 1 (primary outcome).

i) ROIs analysis: Wilcoxon comparison paired tests will be performed to assess differences in [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P uptake before and after DIO diet. Sample size calculation (n = 18) was performed for the main outcome of this study, using G-power (28) with the objective to detect a 20 % difference in radiotracer uptake before and after diet with a 10-20 % variability, alpha risk 5 % and a power of 80 %. Due to multiple comparison on 5 regions tested, Bonferonni correction will be applied to considered p < 0.01 as significant.

ii) Voxel-based analysis: SPM12 (Wellcome Trust Center for Neuroimaging, London; UK) will be used to compare DIO group longitudinally (baseline vs. 10 weeks) using the statistical parametric mapping approach. The comparisons of parametric images between the two time-points will be performed voxel by voxel using a paired t-test analysis. Cluster forming threshold will be set at p < 0.001 (uncorrected). Clusters with an extent of at least 60 voxels (thus matching the raw voxel size of PET) and with p < 0.05 FWE corrected, or with p < 0.001 uncorrected if they belong to regions for which we have an a priori hypothesis, will be considered significant.

Hypothesis 2 (secondary outcome): Kruskal-Wallis test, with Mann-Whitney bilateral post-hoc tests, will be performed to assess [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P binding differences between control, Zucker and DIO groups. No formal sample size calculation was performed for this exploratory analysis. n = 6, as commonly used in preclinical imaging studies, was chosen for control diet and Zucker groups.

Hypothesis 3 (secondary outcome): exploratory Spearman correlation analysis will be performed between MRI measures (change in fat volume or % over the 10-week period) and [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P PET measures (regional SUVr changes over the 10-week period). Student t test will be performed to assess differences in slope of the regression curve between each group. All p-value will be set at 0.05.

Preliminary results from pilot experiments

We first performed a pilot study to validate the chosen diet and to test the MRI protocol. Three male Wistar rats (Charles River Laboratories®; 5-6 weeks old, 188 ± 13 g) were fed with high-fat high-sucrose diet (SAFE® U8955, 246 HF, composition in energy content: proteins 15.9 %, lipids 45.5 % and nitrogen-free extract 38.6 %) for 10 weeks. All rats underwent two MRI imaging sessions (as described in the Methods section): first, before starting diet and second three weeks later. Mean weight were 230 ± 11 g, 406 ± 25 g and 625 ± 53 g at week 0, 3 and 10 respectively. Mean body fat were 9.7 ± 2.2 % and 25.2 ± 3.7 % at week 0 and 3. Mean fat volume were 25 ± 6 cm³ and 113 ± 26 cm³. Rat 2 performed an extra MRI at week 5 to assess the ability to perform the MRI-protocol with a weight of 500 g, body fat was 35.2 % and fat volume was 214 cm³. Figure 1A showed MRI fat images for rat 2 over 5 weeks. All rats responded to the DIO model as they rapidly gained weight, increased body fat percentage and did not showed adverse events due to the diet. A group of 2-3 Sprague-Dawley CD rats (Charles River Laboratories®; 5-6 weeks old, 188 ± 13 g) underwent a similar protocol and yielded a more modest, and more variable increase in body weight and fat % (data not shown), hence justifying our choice to run the study with Wistar animals.

[¹⁸F]2FNQ1P has already shown its ability to target 5-HT₆ receptor in *in-vivo* preclinical studies (24,29) and also to show significant differences in 5-HT₆ expression in *in-vitro* study (30). Because the radiotracer was previously shown to be a Pgp substrate in rats, we assessed the effect and repeatability of the [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P PET uptake in animals premedicated with tariquidar, a third generation Pgp inhibitor, to increase BBB crossing in rats. Three rats performed a baseline PET with NaCl pre-injection and a “test-retest” PET with tariquidar pre-injection (as described in the Methods section), over a one-week period. For each imaging test, Standard Uptake Value (SUV) of regions was normalized with white matter cerebellum SUV to obtain a ratio (SUVr). Regions which showed important binding for

[¹⁸F]2FNQ1P were known to express 5-HT₆ receptors: striatum (caudate, putamen), hippocampus and cerebral cortex (cingulate and frontal). Standard deviation for each region between test and retest were all below 10 % (Table 1). Figure 1B shows PET images with NaCl premedication and tariquidar test-retest in one rat. NaCl condition did not showed satisfying BBB cross due to Pgp efflux. Using tariquidar, images showed a strong and repeatable brain penetration. In addition, as already shown by others groups (31), similar dose tariquidar treatment was devoid of toxicity in contrast to the commonly used cyclosporin A treatment, thus allowing repeated use in animals. We also assessed the feasibility to perform a late, 20-min static scan rather than a dynamic 60-min scan. Binding potentials determined from the 60 min dynamic scan (simplified reference tissue modelling with white matter cerebellum as the reference region) were significantly correlated with the SUV of the 40 to 60 time-frame (Spearman correlation coefficient = 0.90, p-value < 0.0001). Through this pilot experiment, we demonstrate our ability to perform a repeatable *in-vivo* quantification of 5-HT₆ density in rats using [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P in a 20 min μ PET scan with tariquidar premedication. This will enable us to scan up to 5 animals from a single radiosynthesis. Hence the entire protocol will be conducted with 12 imaging sessions of 5 animals (each session composed of 3 DIO rats, 1 control rat, 1 Zucker rat). We envisioned the study to be performed within a 6-month period.

In conclusion, we here propose an original imaging study for understanding the physiopathology of obesity and the implication of 5-HT₆ receptors in this chronic disease. Our preliminary results suggest it is well suited for a registered report publication type.

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Table 1. Results of the pilot study using [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P with tariquidar premedication to assess 5-HT₆ density. Results are expressed as SUVR (normalized SUV ratio to white matter cerebellum).

Region	Side	Rat	SUVR test	SUVR retest	Standard deviation
Caudate Putamen	Left	1	1.33	1.48	10 %
		2	1.41	1.46	4 %
		3	1.50	1.51	1 %
	Right	1	1.33	1.36	2 %
		2	1.41	1.46	4 %
		3	1.50	1.52	1 %
Hypothalamus	Left	1	1.11	1.25	10 %
		2	1.20	1.25	4 %
		3	1.30	1.20	7 %
	Right	1	1.11	1.14	2 %
		2	1.20	1.25	4 %
		3	1.30	1.17	9 %
Hippocampus	Left	1	1.33	1.48	10 %
		2	1.41	1.46	4 %
		3	1.50	1.54	2 %
	Right	1	1.33	1.36	2 %
		2	1.41	1.46	4 %
		3	1.40	1.39	1 %
Frontal Cortex	Left	1	1.22	1.36	10 %
		2	1.30	1.36	4 %
		3	1.40	1.39	0 %
	Right	1	1.22	1.36	10 %
		2	1.30	1.36	4 %
		3	1.30	1.42	9 %
Temporal Cortex	Left	1	1.33	1.25	6 %
		2	1.20	1.25	4 %
		3	1.30	1.25	3 %
	Right	1	1.33	1.36	2 %
		2	1.30	1.25	4 %
		3	1.40	1.39	0 %

Figure 1. (A) Whole-body MRI fat images of rat n°2 with DIO (white contrast represented body fat). Body fat percentage measured with concurrent spectroscopy was 9.7 %, 25.2 % and 35.2 % for week 0, 3 and 5 respectively. (B) Coronal [¹⁸F]2FNQ1P *in-vivo* PET images of rat n°1 after NaCl premedication and test-retest tariquidar premedication (images summed for 60 min on MRI template).

